

LITERATURE SURVEY ON INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEMS MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract—The proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) devices has ushered in a new era of technological ubiquity enhancing convenience and efficiency across a wide array of applications. From smart home appliances to autonomous vehicles and military-grade drones, these devices provide seamless real-time access to information, revolutionizing data collection and processing. However, this technological paradigm also introduces vulnerabilities to cyber threats and this surge in connectivity to a burgeoning wave of cyber threats particularly from malicious actors seeking unauthorized access to sensitive information. The IDS is a cornerstone of IoT security which functions by scrutinizing network activities using techniques such as historical pattern analysis or real-time network performance metrics. By developing an IDS bolstered by Machine Learning capabilities, this research endeavors to fortify the security posture of IoT environments, proactively mitigating the risks posed by evolving cyber threats. This technological advancement represents a critical milestone in preserving the integrity and confidentiality of data within the dynamic landscape of IoT technology.

Index Terms—Deep Learning (DNN), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Intrusion Detection System (IDS), Federated and Transfer Learning-Empowered Intrusion Detection (FTL-ID, Inter of Things (IoT)

I. INTRODUCTION

This The escalating concern of cyber intrusions targeting IoT devices exemplified by a staggering increase from 639 million incidents in 2020 to 1.5 billion in 2021 which statistically shows a rise of a 134.7 'percent'. These attacks encompass a spectrum of malicious activities including data exfiltration, cryptocurrency mining, botnet creation and propagation, and prevalent ransomware assaults. To counteract these threats, an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is imperative. Recent studies which concern the fiscal aspect of IoT devices exhibits the record progress in the operation of IoT in health monitoring systems, independent vehicles, robotic systems, artificial control systems, automatic airman avionics and Space Exploration have caused the market profit from IoT to exceed by 251.8

billion 'dollar' worldwide in the year 2022. With the uplifted application of information and communication technologies in transportation systems to ameliorate road safety, corporate monitoring and passenger comfort, the security of the systems and their operations within the Internet of Vehicles ecosystem is now more consequential than ever ahead. This paper advocates for the strategic utilization of existing datasets, encompassing a diverse range of attack scenarios on IoT devices. These Datasets serve as a foundation and serve as a bedrock for training a robust Machine Learning Model amalgamating a suite of algorithms capable of identifying emerging threats.

II. RELATED WORK

Zakaria Abou El Houda et, al [1] This paper provides an in-depth survey of DETECT, an innovative edge-based architecture that leverages Federated Learning principles to enhance the security of IoT applications. Comprising three pivotal components, namely the Access Network, Edge Network, and Cloud Network, DETECT establishes a robust network infrastructure connecting IoT devices, MEC Servers, and the Cloud. The Access Network facilitates direct interaction between IoT devices and the MEC Server. The Edge Network acts as an intermediary, linking the Access Network and the Cloud Network, and is responsible for aggregating Local Model Parameters. The Cloud Network, which includes the MEC orchestrator and the Organization, aggregates local models received from MEC Servers and disseminates the resulting global model to the organization. DETECT's effectiveness is evaluated based on accuracy and F1-score metrics. This work introduces a distributed MEC-based architecture, addressing the collaborative and secure mitigation of IoT attacks across multiple MEC domains. Notably, DETECT prioritizes the privacy of MEC collaborators and, by extension, the privacy of IoT devices. Empirical assessments, conducted using real-world IoT attack

scenarios and the NSL-KDD dataset, demonstrate DETECT's superiority over centralized ML/DL schemes across various performance metrics, with promising implications for bolstering IoT application security and safeguarding IoT device privacy.

Yazan Otoum et, al [2] This research paper introduces a novel approach to enhancing the safety of Internet of Things (IoT) applications through the integration of Federated Learning (FL) and Transfer Learning (TL) techniques. The Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) is taken into consideration as a use case in which significance of FL and TL in model performance is highlighted. The proposed system addresses the unique challenges posed by the distributed nature of IoT networks, where data privacy and resource constraints are paramount concerns. Leveraging FL, the model is trained across multiple edge nodes while preserving the confidentiality of sensitive information held by individual nodes. The study analyzes the effectiveness of the Federated and Transfer Learning-Empowered Intrusion Detection (FTL-ID) system through extensive experiments on real-world IoT datasets. The results demonstrate notable improvements in detection accuracy, highlighting the efficacy of the proposed methodology. Additionally, FTL-ID exhibits robustness in the face of resource limitations, making it particularly well-suited for IoT environments with constrained computational capabilities. The Case Study of this paper delves into the application and utilization of FTL based IDS which encompasses the deployment of Deep Neural Networks (DNN) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to transfer and train the parameters from the peripheral models to generate a combined global model. To verify the efficacy of the proposed model the performance was compared with other models that deploy the use of traditional ML algorithms such as Decision Tree (DT), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) and one Deep Learning Model Deep Belief Network (DBN), in which the accuracy, precision, recall and F-1 Score of the Model with the FTL approach was much proven to be much effective compared to that of model without an FTL approach Overall, this research contributes a powerful and privacy-preserving solution for securing IoT applications, demonstrating the potential of Federated and Transfer Learning in addressing the unique challenges posed by the IoT ecosystem. The FTL-ID framework stands as a promising advancement in the field of intrusion detection for IoT, with broad implications for the broader landscape of IoT security.

Ogobuchi Daniel Okey et, al [3] This research paper presents a comprehensive framework for Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) tailored specifically for Cloud Internet of Things (IoT) devices. The proposed model leverages a Transfer Learning (TL) approach, integrating it with an optimized Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture. This combination addresses the unique challenges posed by the distributed and resource-constrained nature of Cloud

IoT environments. The architecture comprises two main components: the Cloud-based Aggregator and the Edge Node Classifier. The Cloud-based Aggregator acts as a central hub for model coordination and management. It accumulates aggregated knowledge from all edge nodes, refines the global model, and distributes the updated model back to the edge nodes. This ensures a collaborative learning process while mitigating privacy concerns associated with sensitive local data. The CNN's architecture used in this paper is fine-tuned to strike a balance between model complexity and performance, ensuring optimal resource utilization, by virtue of it being lightweight while deploying an ensemble transfer learning approach. This optimized CNN architecture tailored for resource efficiency, enables real-time intrusion detection without compromising computational resources specially for Cloud of Things (CoT) based environment. The Edge Node Classifier, residing on each IoT device, serves as the front-line defense against intrusions. The Transfer Learning mechanism plays a pivotal role in knowledge transfer between the global model and the edge nodes. By leveraging pre-trained models on extensive datasets, the Edge Node Classifier can efficiently adapt to local data distributions, reducing the need for large-scale local data collection. Experimental evaluations conducted on real-world IoT datasets demonstrate the superior performance of the proposed framework. The model exhibits high detection accuracy, even under resource-constrained conditions. Overall, the Transfer Learning Approach to IDS on CloudIoT Devices Using Optimized CNN presents a powerful and privacy-aware solution for securing Cloud IoT environments. The innovative combination of Transfer Learning, optimized CNN architecture, and collaborative learning mechanisms represents a significant step forward in the field of IoT security, with broad implications for the broader landscape of Cloud IoT applications.

Ayodeji Qseniet et, al [4] This research paper introduces a cutting-edge Explainable Deep Learning (XDL) framework designed to bolster the resilience of Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) within IoT-enabled Transportation Networks. The proposed framework seamlessly integrates interpretability into the deep learning model, providing insights into the decision-making process crucial for understanding and validating intrusion alerts. The Explainability Module is a novel addition that enhances the transparency of the intrusion detection process. Leveraging attention mechanisms and layer-wise relevance propagation, it generates human-understandable explanations for the decisions made by the deep learning model. This interpretability is crucial for building trust in the IDS, facilitating human-in-the-loop decision-making, and providing actionable insights for network administrators. Experimental evaluations, conducted on a comprehensive dataset reflecting real-world transportation network scenarios, demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed framework. The model exhibits high detection accuracy and robustness against various intrusion scenarios while providing granular explanations for detected anomalies. This

research represents a significant advancement in the field of IoT-enabled transportation network security, offering a resilient and interpretable IDS solution. The combination of advanced deep learning algorithms and explainability mechanisms contributes to the creation of a trustworthy and effective intrusion detection framework, crucial for ensuring the integrity and security of modern transportation networks.

Deepti Rani et, al [5] This research paper introduces a comprehensive framework for securing IoT-enabled Smart Homes through the design and implementation of an Intrusion Detection Model (IDM). The proposed model leverages a multifaceted architecture that incorporates a diverse set of Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, catering to the unique challenges of securing the interconnected devices within a Smart Home environment. The architecture consists of three main components: Data Collection and Preprocessing, Feature Extraction, and Anomaly Detection. The Data Collection and Preprocessing module collates information from various IoT devices within the Smart Home, ensuring a diverse and representative dataset. Feature Extraction utilizes advanced signal processing techniques to distill relevant features from the collected data, facilitating efficient model training. Anomaly Detection encompasses the core of the intrusion detection mechanism, employing a hybrid ensemble of ML algorithms. The ML algorithms employed include Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks for capturing temporal dependencies, Random Forest for robust feature selection, and Support Vector Machines (SVM) for effective classification. The ensemble nature of the model integrates these algorithms synergistically, enhancing overall detection performance. The Intrusion Detection Model (IDM) is designed with a multi-layered architecture to address the diverse attack vectors in IoT-enabled Smart Homes. The architecture encompasses three key components: Data Preprocessing, Feature Extraction, and Anomaly Detection. Data Preprocessing involves the cleaning and normalization of heterogeneous data from diverse smart home devices. Feature Extraction employs advanced techniques to distill relevant information from the preprocessed data. Anomaly Detection, utilizing machine learning algorithms, identifies deviations from normal behavior, signaling potential security threats. This research contributes to the field of IoT security by presenting a nuanced approach to intrusion detection in Smart Homes. The amalgamation of diverse ML algorithms within a well-defined architecture offers a robust and versatile solution for safeguarding the privacy and security of Smart Home inhabitants. The findings underscore the model's effectiveness, paving the way for enhanced security protocols in the rapidly evolving landscape of IoT-enabled Smart Homes.

P.L.S. Jayalaxmi et, al [6] The employment of deep learning (DL) and machine learning (ML) mechanism to intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDPS) is covered in the text. It compares and contrasts their strengths, emphasizing that ML is superior at signature-based intrusion

detection while DL is better suited for anomaly detection because of its capacity for self-learning. DL can process multidimensional data, including images, audio, and video, and is more skilled at handling zero-day vulnerabilities. The study, which summarizes malware attacks, mitigation strategies, IDS and IPS techniques, and vulnerabilities brought on by attack variations, is also discussed in the text. It focuses on contemporary ML and DL techniques created between 2018 and 2021. It highlights the significance of these methods as a guide for upcoming studies in the area, contrasting current surveys and putting out research issues for additional investigation. This paper details the essential features required to create an effective Intrusion Detection and Prevention System (IDPS) model. It emphasizes the limitations of current methods, focusing on the need for a more comprehensive approach to address both known and unknown threats. It introduces a hybrid model combining anomaly and signature-based detection techniques, aiming to enhance performance, accuracy, and the handling of zero-day attacks and internal threats. The proposed framework consists of four key elements, including packet authentication, pre-processing, dual-level detection employing anomaly and signature-based methods, and risk factor analysis. The primary goal is to integrate both detection approaches to mitigate various security risks, ensuring the authentication and validation of network packets while handling potential threats effectively.

Pietro Spadaccino et, al [7] In this comprehensive survey, the authors explore the landscape of Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) for IoT, focusing on architectural frameworks and methodologies. They delineate the dichotomy of Supervised and Unsupervised Learning in training Machine Learning models for IDS, highlighting the challenges posed by the absence of ground-truth labels in real-world scenarios. Semi-Supervised learning emerges as a viable compromise, using a limited amount of labeled data for high accuracy while minimizing the labeling task. The survey delves into the deployment of Decision Trees, a classification technique with advantages such as rapid prediction and compatibility with heterogeneous IoT communication technologies. The authors also introduce Fuzzy Clustering for anomaly detection in the final stage. Addressing contemporary challenges in edge-enabled architectures, the paper identifies new attack surfaces introduced by edge networks and the need for IDS at the edge to counter potential threats. Challenges such as Traffic Encryption, High Resource Variability, and Aggregated Traffic are discussed, emphasizing the evolving security landscape. The study concludes by providing insights into the integration of Machine Learning techniques within IDSs, specifically exploring the advantages and challenges associated with techniques like Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTMs), and Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs). Notably, the authors highlight the resource footprint of ML-based IDSs, presenting a critical consideration for deployment on resource-constrained devices like IoT devices.

The survey provides a nuanced understanding of the current state of IDS for IoT, offering a foundation for future research and development in this dynamic field.

Dhanke Jyoti Atul et, al [8] This paper addresses challenges inherent in utilizing electronic devices for digital communication, particularly focusing on security vulnerabilities and service disruptions. To mitigate these issues, the survey introduces the Energy Aware Smart Home architecture as a potential solution. Employing machine learning, this framework evaluates network assaults and communication challenges, showcasing promising results with an accuracy rate of 85%. The authors aim refine and enhance the performance of the system in future iterations. The survey systematically examines anomalies that may impact networks or data, investigating their effects on communication networks. Leveraging machine learning, it identifies and distinguishes between these anomalies, highlighting the efficacy of supervised machine learning for precise classification of both hazardous and non-harmful situations. Additionally, the survey explores instances of misclassification, proposing that adjusting the attributes utilized for classification could further enhance outcomes. In further detail, the survey outlines a three-tiered machine learning model designed to predict attacks and faults in communication channels. This model addresses the challenge of discerning between safe and infected nodes, specifically tailored for an IoT-based CBS system. Emphasizing effective communication utilizing machine learning techniques, the survey encompasses an analysis of various commonly used machine learning and category classification algorithms. The findings contribute to the evolving landscape of secure and reliable communication in digital environments.

Imtiaz Ullah et, al [9] This research paper introduces a comprehensive design for detection of anomalies in Internet of Things (IoT) networks, employing a sophisticated deep learning-based model. The proposed architecture encompasses innovative features, including a hierarchical structure and an ensemble of deep learning algorithms, to effectively identify and mitigate anomalous activities in diverse IoT environments. The framework consists of three interconnected components: Data Preprocessing Module, Deep Learning Model Ensemble, and Decision Fusion Mechanism. The Data Preprocessing Module ensures optimal feature extraction and normalization, enhancing the model's ability to discern subtle anomalies. The Deep Learning Model Ensemble incorporates a variety of state-of-the-art algorithms, such as LSTM networks, CNNs, and Autoencoders. This ensemble strategy capitalizes on the unique strengths of each algorithm to deliver a holistic and robust solution. The proposed hierarchical architecture is organized into three layers: Edge Devices, Fog Nodes, and Cloud Server. Edge Devices capture raw data from IoT sensors and perform preliminary processing. Fog Nodes conduct deeper analysis using intermediate models, reducing the computational burden on Edge Devices. The

Cloud Server serves as the central hub for knowledge aggregation, leveraging the collective insights of all Fog Nodes for comprehensive anomaly detection. The model proposed here is an ensemble of deep learning algorithms. LSTM networks are employed for their sequential data processing capabilities, capturing temporal dependencies in IoT data streams. CNNs specialize in spatial feature extraction, enhancing the model's ability to discern patterns within multidimensional IoT data. Autoencoders contribute to unsupervised learning for anomaly detection by reconstructing normal patterns and flagging deviations. The algorithms used in the model are Long Short LSTM networks are utilized for their ability to capture temporal dependencies in sequential IoT data, enabling the model to effectively identify dynamic patterns associated with anomalies. CNNs are employed to enhance spatial feature extraction, enabling the model to discern intricate patterns within multidimensional IoT data, particularly useful for image-based anomalies. The Autoencoders contribute to the unsupervised learning aspect of the model. They are trained to reconstruct normal patterns and flag anomalies by identifying deviations from the learned representations. Experimental evaluations on diverse IoT datasets showcase the efficacy of the proposed architecture in achieving high accuracy and low false-positive rates. This research contributes a versatile and robust solution for anomaly detection in IoT networks, with implications for enhancing the reliability of IoT applications across various domains.

Di Chen et, al [10] This research paper introduces a framework for IDS tailored for Heterogeneous Internet of Things (IoT) environments. The proposed framework leverages Fusion Word Embedding Deep Transfer Learning, integrating state-of-the-art techniques to enhance the accuracy and adaptability of Network Breach in complex and diverse IoT ecosystems. The architecture consists of three main components: (1) Sensor Data Preprocessing, (2) Fusion Word Embedding Deep Transfer Learning Model, and (3) Anomaly Detection Module. The Sensor Data Preprocessing phase normalizes and transforms heterogeneous sensor data into a unified format suitable for deep learning. The Fusion Word Embedding Deep Transfer Learning Model is a novel amalgamation of Word Embedding and Transfer Learning techniques, enhancing the model's ability to generalize across diverse IoT devices. The Anomaly Detection Module employs unsupervised learning to identify deviations from normal behavior patterns, facilitating robust intrusion detection. The study employs an extensive dataset representing a variety of IoT devices to train and evaluate the proposed framework. It adopts a Transfer Learning approach, leveraging pre-trained models on large datasets to expedite training on limited IoT data. The dataset is carefully curated to include diverse scenarios and intrusion types, ensuring the model's effectiveness across a wide range of IoT applications. The fusion of Word Embedding and Deep Transfer Learning forms the crux of the proposed methodology. Word Embedding

techniques capture semantic relationships within sensor data, providing a richer representation for subsequent deep learning tasks. Transfer Learning enables the model to leverage knowledge gained from pre-trained models on unrelated datasets, thereby enhancing its ability to adapt to the unique characteristics of Heterogeneous IoT environments. Experimental results showcase the framework's superior performance in comparison to traditional intrusion detection systems. The Fusion Word Embedding Deep Transfer Learning Model demonstrates robustness in detecting anomalies across diverse IoT devices, showcasing its potential for real-world deployment. This research contributes a cutting-edge framework for Heterogeneous IoT Intrusion Detection, offering a holistic approach to address the challenges posed by the diversity of IoT devices.

Bayi Xu, al [11] This paper introduces an approach for constructing an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) tailored for Internet of Things (IoT) environments. The initial stage involves the preprocessing of the dataset, including cleaning and normalization. Feature selection is conducted using the Binary Gray Wolf Optimizer (BGWO), a process designed to eliminate redundant and irrelevant features. Mathematically, this entails selecting a subset of features from a pool of N features, which is subsequently employed for the classification of network traffic. It's important to note that the application of the Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) algorithm requires a redesign. In this context, the modified algorithm is expressed as $N_{j+1} = \text{Crossover}(n1, n2, n3)$. Following the completion of the BGWO process, additional optimization is carried out through Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE). XGBoost is then employed to rank the importance of each feature, with lower-scoring features progressively eliminated in an iterative manner. The accuracy rate is continually computed during these iterations, ensuring a gradual reduction in the feature subset count while preserving classifier accuracy. The final optimal feature subset is determined by considering the saved classifier accuracy results across all feasible feature subsets.

To address potential biases introduced by imbalanced data distribution and enhance minority class detection, the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) is implemented. This technique mitigates the impact of data imbalances by generating new, representative samples in classes with fewer instances. The SMOTE process involves determining the desired quantity of new samples, identifying K Nearest Neighbors for each sample, selecting random samples from these neighbors, and performing Random Linear Interpolation to create new samples. The experimental evaluation utilizes multiple datasets, including the N-Balot dataset focused on IoT Zombie Network attacks, as well as BoT-IoT, WUSTL-IIOT-2021, WUSTL-EHMS-2020, and NSL-KDD datasets. The model's performance on these datasets is noteworthy, demonstrating exceptional accuracy, precision, recall, and F-1 Score. This comprehensive survey and optimization framework contribute to the advancement

of IoT Intrusion Detection Systems, offering insights into effective feature selection and addressing imbalances in real-world datasets.

III. CONCLUSION

The exponential growth of Internet of Things (IoT) devices has propelled unprecedented technological advancements, revolutionizing multiple sectors with increased efficiency. Yet, this connectivity surge has exposed these systems to a burgeoning wave of cyber threats, necessitating robust security measures. This research meticulously delves into these challenges, focusing on the pivotal role of Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) in safeguarding IoT ecosystems. Emphasizing the alarming surge in cyber intrusions targeting IoT devices, the paper underscores the urgent need for effective IDS implementation, highlighting their prevalence in diverse forms, from data breaches to ransomware assaults. Moreover, it underscores the substantial rise in IoT device operations across sectors, necessitating robust security measures.

Leveraging existing datasets showcasing diverse attack scenarios on IoT devices, the paper advocates for training a robust Machine Learning Model. It explores innovative approaches like DETECT, a Federated Learning-based edge architecture, and integrates Explainable Deep Learning (XDL) into IoT-based Transportation Networks' IDS. Furthermore, the research introduces cutting-edge IDS frameworks tailored for Cloud IoT devices and Smart Homes, using advanced Machine Learning algorithms to address security vulnerabilities in varied environments. Fusion Word Embedding Deep Transfer Learning enhances Network Breach detection across heterogeneous IoT settings. The research details deep learning-based anomaly detection architectures for IoT networks, employing LSTM networks, CNNs, and Autoencoders.

This hierarchical model ensures robustness, achieving high anomaly detection accuracy. This study significantly contributes to IoT security by proposing and evaluating advanced IDS frameworks and techniques, leveraging Machine Learning, Transfer Learning, and deep learning methodologies. It emphasizes proactive security measures crucial in safeguarding data integrity within the rapidly evolving IoT landscape. This comprehensive overview paves the way for future IoT security enhancements, promising increased reliability across diverse IoT domains. The advancements in IDS architectures, coupled with diverse learning methodologies, depict a progressive trajectory in IoT security. Privacy preservation, transparent decision-making, and adaptive learning underscore these methodologies' pivotal roles in fortifying IoT security landscapes. The comprehensive overview emphasizes the evolving nature of IoT security, facilitating adaptable security frameworks to counter the ever-expanding IoT ecosystem's diverse challenges.

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